

METHODS USED IN TEACHING THE UZBEKI LANGUAGE AND PROBLEMS OF THEIR IMPROVEMENT

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Abstract: This scientific article analyzes the methods used in teaching the Uzbek language and issues of their improvement. Educational methods developed on the basis of interactive, communicative, linguistic and innovative approaches are of great importance in the process of effective teaching of the Uzbek language. The article discusses the uniqueness of these methods, their effectiveness, and ways to modernize them. It is also justified the necessity of enrichment of practical training and educational materials for learners of the Uzbek language, introduction of technologies that help the development of linguistic competence.

Key words: teaching Uzbek language, methods, interactive approach, communicative method, linguistic competence, innovative technologies, modernization of education, non-traditional methods, pedagogical technologies.

Enter. The mother tongue teaches the student to think independently, to fully express his thoughts orally and in writing. The student's level of literacy, his place in social life is built on the basis of knowledge and skills acquired from his mother tongue . It is known that each national language, in addition to adequately reflecting the material world, fully expresses the spiritual world, its sorrows and joys. A person has the opportunity to express his attitude towards everything , and this opportunity is always brought to light through certain forms of language. Modern information and pedagogical technologies are effectively used in mother tongue education in addition to traditional methods in order to convey, feel, feel and use it wisely . o

The Uzbek language occupies an important place as the state language in our country, and its education also requires special attention. Today, one of the main tasks is to introduce effective approaches to teaching the Uzbek language , to implement innovative methods in the educational process. In this article, the methods used in the process of teaching the Uzbek language and the issues of their improvement are extensively analyzed. b

Empirical studies of mother tongue teaching increasingly emphasize the increasing importance of methods and approaches in the effective teaching of students' mother tongue. The purpose of teaching the mother tongue is to help students develop interpersonal communication skills, establish a strong cultural identity, and participate fully in the socio-economic and political discourses of their countries . Russia : 21.10.2024)

The main part. What does the word method mean? Method is a Greek word that means "study" or "way of knowing". This concept has philosophical and didactic meanings. In the philosophical sense, the concept of "method" means observing the phenomena of nature and society and approaching reality from a scientific point of view. In the didactic sense, this concept refers to ways of equipping students with knowledge, skills and abilities. Issues

related to the teaching of certain subjects are studied by a special methodology. Therefore, educational methods are of great interest to both scientists and methodologists . Among the main methods used in teaching the Uzbek language, the following can be distinguished:

1. Grammar translation method : This method is one of the oldest methods of language teaching , based on the study of grammatical rules and translation of words.
2. Communicative approach : This method is based on engaging students in the language through communicative skills. The lessons are aimed at developing communication and speech competence.
3. Interactive methods : ensuring the active participation of students in the learning process is carried out by using various games, role-playing games and group work.
4. Methods based on innovative technologies : Presentations, online platforms, interactive materials are included in the process of teaching the Uzbek language with the help of modern technologies.

In order to increase the effectiveness of the existing methods in teaching the Uzbek language, the following directions are proposed:

- Technological approaches : Interactive tools, mobile applications and online learning platforms can be of great importance in teaching the Uzbek language.
- New didactic materials : There is a need to enrich educational materials, implement multilingual methods and use multimedia tools.
- Differentiated approach : Applying individual and group approaches according to students' knowledge level and abilities makes the language teaching process more effective.

The student's knowledge on a certain topic, his subjective evaluation and opinion serve as a "communication filter" for the teacher to understand and accept him. The organization of foreign language teaching using the interactive learning model confirms the correctness of the following conclusions:

1. If students are given the opportunity to approach the learning of certain educational materials based on their personal experience, the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities are acquired when necessary;
2. If the teacher actively supports the students' educational tools , they learn very well;
3. If the teacher, firstly, is able to choose effective means of learning based on the capabilities of the students, and secondly, takes into account their opinion, even if it does not agree with his own opinion, then the students will learn what they want. they study science.

In the process of teaching the Uzbek language to students, the presence of an interactive process not only negates the "power" of the teacher, but also makes it possible to assess the student's level of knowledge, identify achievements and shortcomings. Another advantage of the interactive process :

- expression of students' personal opinion;
- to defend one's views;
- listening to other people's opinions, summarizing them, identifying the main, important and real ones from the opinions expressed, developing the ability to draw conclusions;
- the correct and effective use of interactive methods in the educational process consists in improving skills and competencies.

Therefore, a skillful and artistic approach to the educational process, organizing it according to needs, is one of the important conditions for raising a perfect person, and each student has his own idea .

It is known that today there are more than a hundred types of interactive methods, most of which have been tested and have given good results. Effective results can be achieved in the lesson by using the widely used methods - "Cluster", "Brainstorming", "Continue", "Presentation", "Blitz survey", "Problem situation". "Sinquain", "Reverse Test", "Wheel of Mind" methods are used in the part of the lesson to ask about the passed topic, "Insert", "Pinboard", "Zinama-Zina", "Boomerang" technologies in the part of explaining the new topic, in the part of strengthening the topic Graphic organizers such as Venn Diagram, Fishbone, Why?, How?, Concept Chart, Lily Flower, and Concept Analysis, T-Table, Resume, The use of "Sunflower", "Charkhpalak" methods, "FSMU", "Cluster", "BBXB" methods for homework help to ensure the effectiveness of the lesson and increase the knowledge of students. In addition to the above-mentioned interactive methods, didactic games such as "Yes...no", "Find the owner of the definition", "Who am I?", "Domino" can be used in the native language and literature classes. During the game, the students behave freely and want to show their knowledge. As a result, confidence and determination appear in the student. Learns to engage in debate. He is used to justifying his opinion. The age and level of education of students should be taken into account .

Summary. In conclusion, we can say that modern methods of teaching the Uzbek language are important in attracting students to the language, developing linguistic competence and forming practical skills. Increasing the effectiveness of teaching by improving the methods serves to strengthen the position of the Uzbek language in the international arena. At the same time, the introduction of new technologies and didactic materials into the educational process makes language teaching more interactive and attractive.

In the method of observing language evidence, grammar, orthography is widely used in the study of the written language. When analyzing language facts, two directions are taken as a basis.

1. Observing language evidence. Under the guidance of the teacher, students conduct observations on some aspect of language phenomena based on a specific plan.
2. Method of exercises. Students' knowledge and skills acquired in the mother tongue are strengthened through various exercises. As a result, students :
 - a) learn knowledge consciously;
 - b) will be able to apply knowledge in practice;
 - e) thinking skills also increase, during the exercise they observe, compare, summarize language evidence more;
 - f) they will have the opportunity to improve their speech culture.

Literature is the art of words. Therefore, one cannot understand the beauty and power of literature without mastering the native language . We can see that the content of the lessons of mother tongue and literary science consists of regularly increasing the student's interest and attention to the word, explaining to them the importance of the word and its place in various texts .

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